

Charged Particle Beam Penetrating a Slab of Matter Optimization for Minimal Output Emittance

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1 Introduction

If a thin piece of matter is penetrated by a particle beam, the action of the angular scattering may be approximated by the assumption, that all the scattering takes place at the degrader midpoint and gives there an additional angular distribution. Whereas if the degrader is thick that the shape of the occupied phase space ellipse changes considerably due to drift during the penetration, this effect has to be taken into account.

Assuming a Gauss profile for the angular scattering distribution due to the penetration of a small layer, a differential equation containing drift and scattering action has been derived. This equation turned out to be easily solvable by continued integrations.

In the thin degrader approximation the increase of the beam emittance may be kept very small by focusing the beam onto a very small spot at the degrader midpoint. Whereas in the more realistic model here described a minimal increase of the beam emittance was found for the optimum case.

2 Recapitulation of Linear Beam Transport Formalism

If the trajectories of particles in a beam deviate only slightly from a reference orbit, these deviations with respect to the reference particle fulfil linear differential equations, which can be treated by a matrix formalism [1-4]. The meanings of the coordinates to describe the motions are shown in fig. (1). The relative impulse derivation $\Delta p/p$ is assumed to give only a small influence for the emittance increase and therefore it is omitted. When these particle coordinates are written as a vector, the new particle coordinates at another point of the beam line are in first (linear) order approximation

$$\begin{pmatrix} x \\ \vartheta \\ y \\ \varphi \end{pmatrix}_{(t_2)} = \begin{pmatrix} R_{11} & R_{12} & R_{13} & R_{14} \\ R_{21} & R_{22} & R_{23} & R_{24} \\ R_{31} & R_{32} & R_{33} & R_{34} \\ R_{41} & R_{42} & R_{43} & R_{44} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} x \\ \vartheta \\ y \\ \varphi \end{pmatrix}_{(t_1)}$$

where the matrix is the Transport matrix between the points t_1 and t_2 . In pure Quadrupole

Figure 1: Particle trajectories with respect to a reference particle

fields (no dipole, skew - quadrupole or higher multipole components) this general transport matrix splits into smaller (2×2) matrices. So particle coordinates in x - direction are transformed separately in the following way :

$$\vec{x}(t_2) = \begin{pmatrix} x \\ \vartheta \end{pmatrix}_{(t_2)} = \begin{pmatrix} R_{11} & R_{12} \\ R_{21} & R_{22} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} x \\ \vartheta \end{pmatrix}_{(t_1)} = R \vec{x}(t_1)$$

In y - direction an analogous relation holds. For a drift space, which means the absence of any magnetic field, the Transport matrix is derived as follows :

$$\begin{pmatrix} x \\ \vartheta \end{pmatrix}_{(t_2)} = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & t \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} x \\ \vartheta \end{pmatrix}_{(t_1)} = R \vec{x}(t_1) \quad (1)$$

where t means the drift length $t_2 - t_1$.

In order to introduce the σ - Matrix formalism [2] it is assumed, that a bundle of particles is correctly described by an ellipse in the (x, ϑ) space. It is assumed, that points on this ellipse correspond to one standard deviation from the reference particle. This ellipse is given by

$$\vec{x}^T(t_1) \sigma^{-1}(t_1) \vec{x}(t_1) = 1 \quad (2)$$

where σ^{-1} and therefore also σ are symmetric matrices. This ellipse equation is combined with the transport formula to get :

$$\begin{aligned} \vec{x}^T(t_1) \sigma^{-1}(t_1) \vec{x}(t_1) &= \vec{x}^T(t_2) (R^{-1})^T \sigma^{-1}(t_1) R^{-1} \vec{x}(t_2) = \\ &= \vec{x}^T(t_2) \sigma^{-1}(t_2) \vec{x}(t_2) \end{aligned}$$

Thus the σ matrix defining the phase space ellipse is transported by

$$\sigma(t_2) = \left[(R^{-1})^T \sigma(t_1)^{-1} R^{-1} \right]^{-1} = R \sigma(t_1) R^T$$

If this formula is applied for a drift space using equ. (1), one gets

$$\sigma(t_2) = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & t \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \sigma_{11} & \sigma_{12} \\ \sigma_{12} & \sigma_{22} \end{pmatrix}_{(t_1)} \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ t & 1 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \sigma_{11} + 2t\sigma_{12} + t^2\sigma_{22} & \sigma_{12} + t\sigma_{22} \\ \sigma_{12} + t\sigma_{22} & \sigma_{22} \end{pmatrix} \quad (3)$$

3 Angular Scattering Distribution

Mainly by elastic Coulomb scattering a charged particle traversing a piece of matter is scattered by many small angle elastic scatterings. For an entire beam the angular scattering results in a distribution, which is only approximately a Gauss profile. The real distribution gives much higher probability for large angle scattering. However, since the entire effect of the angular straggling in a thick piece of matter is the superposition of many such distributions for small drift lengths, the assumption of a Gauss distribution will cause only a small error. The standard deviation ϑ_{rms} of the scattering distribution is given by [5,6]

$$\vartheta_{rms}^2 = \underbrace{\frac{(14.1 \frac{MeV}{c})^2 Z_B^2}{A_B^2 L_R}}_{=: K} \frac{\Delta t}{(p \beta)^2} \quad (1)$$

where p , β , Z_B and A_B are the momentum per nucleon, the velocity, the charge and the atomic mass of the incoming beam and $\Delta t/L_R$ is the penetrated thickness in radiation lengths. ϑ_{rms} is the standard deviation of the angular distribution in one (say x) direction.

4 Phase Space Ellipse and Density Function Formalism

In a real beam the particles will not occupy the inside of the above defined ellipse with no particles outside the ellipse, but there will be a distribution, which is described by a density function $\rho(x, \vartheta)$. Assuming a Gaussian distribution in x and ϑ coordinate and a constant distribution on the ellipse a two-dimensional density function is defined by :

$$\rho(x, \vartheta) \propto \exp\left(-\frac{\vec{x}^T \sigma^{-1} \vec{x}}{2}\right) = \exp\left(-\frac{x^2}{2\sigma_{22}}\right) \exp\left[-\frac{1}{\sigma_{22} - \sigma_{12}^2/\sigma_{11}} \left(\vartheta - \frac{\sigma_{12}}{\sigma_{11}}x\right)^2\right] \quad (2)$$

For that purpose the phase space ellipse given by equ. 2 is said to correspond to one standard deviation (Unfortunately there exists another convention saying, that this ellipse would correspond to $1/\sqrt{2}$ standard deviation). The corresponding emittance $\pi\epsilon_\sigma = \pi\sqrt{\det \sigma} = \pi\sqrt{\sigma_{11}\sigma_{22} - \sigma_{12}^2}$ defined by the area of the ellipse contains 39.3 % of the trajectories. An other similar ellipse with area $\pi\epsilon$ contains the fraction $1 - \exp(-\frac{\epsilon}{2\epsilon_\sigma})$ of the particles. The more common emittance containing 95 % of the beam is calculated by $\epsilon_{95} = -2\ln(1-0.95)\epsilon_\sigma \sim 6\epsilon_\sigma$. We see, that for a given x the distribution in ϑ is centred at $\vartheta_0 = x\sigma_{12}/\sigma_{11}$ and has a variance

$$V_\vartheta = \sigma_{22} - \frac{\sigma_{12}^2}{\sigma_{11}} \quad (3)$$

This variance of course does not depend on the fixed level of x , which is important for the further calculations. If one integrated over ϑ the variance in x for the whole ellipse would be σ_{11} . But this does not correspond to the width of the ellipse at a given level ϑ . If we rewrite equ. (3) in another form we can show that, in analogy with V_ϑ , the variance in x at any ϑ -level is $V_x = \sigma_{11} - \sigma_{12}^2/\sigma_{22}$. For the simple case of an upright ellipse $\sigma_{12} = 0$, $V_x = \sigma_{11}$ and $V_\vartheta = \sigma_{22}$.

5 σ - Matrix Differential Equation in the Degradar

For ease of calculations the dynamics of the σ -matrix due to angular scattering and due to the well known usual drift are separated. So one gets differential equations for both processes, which are added in order to get the equation determining the entire beam dynamics in the degrader.

Neglecting the influence of usual drift the scattering will broaden the ϑ -distributions for fixed x . The pure angular scattering cannot mix different x -values. Therefore the standard deviation $\sqrt{\sigma_{11}}$ of the x -dependent weight function for the ϑ -distributions remains constant. This implies that σ_{11} remains constant. The center of the ϑ -distributions $x\sigma_{12}/\sigma_{11}$ also will not change, which leads to a constant σ_{12} . For the square of the standard deviation in ϑ -direction the following equation holds :

$$\Delta \left(\sigma_{22} - \frac{\sigma_{12}^2}{\sigma_{11}} \right) = \Delta \sigma_{22} = \frac{d \vartheta_{rms}^2}{d t} \Delta t \quad (7)$$

The last term in this equation may be taken from equation (4). Therefore the influence of the angular scattering onto the σ matrix neglecting usual drift reads in matrix form as

$$\left(\frac{d \sigma}{d t} \right)_{sc} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 \\ 0 & d \vartheta_{rms}^2 / d t \end{pmatrix} \quad (8)$$

In general the term $d \vartheta_{rms}^2 / d t$ will depend on t due to the change of energy of the beam passing through matter.

In order to get the σ -matrix dynamics due to drifting, equation (3) is investigated. For the drift length t the small length $d t$ is inserted. The term quadratic in $d t$ vanishes and the differential equation for the drift influence becomes

$$\left(\frac{d \sigma}{d t} \right)_{dr} = \begin{pmatrix} 2\sigma_{12} & \sigma_{22} \\ \sigma_{22} & 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad (9)$$

Note, that by integrating formula (9) we recover exactly equ. (3) including the t^2 term.

Now including scattering and drifting the entire σ matrix dynamics becomes

$$\frac{d \sigma}{d t} = \left(\frac{d \sigma}{d t} \right)_{sc} + \left(\frac{d \sigma}{d t} \right)_{dr} = \begin{pmatrix} 2\sigma_{12} & \sigma_{22} \\ \sigma_{22} & d \vartheta_{rms}^2 / d t \end{pmatrix} \quad (10)$$

If the dependence of $d \vartheta_{rms}^2 / d t$ w. r. t. the beam line position t is known (using a range table and equ.(4)), this matrix differential equation is solvable by continual integrations. Say at the beginning of the degrader $t = 0$ and the components of σ are designated by an additional index 0. The differential equation for the component σ_{22} has the solution

$$\sigma_{22}(t) = \sigma_{22}^0 + \int_0^t \frac{d \vartheta_{rms}^2}{d s}(s) ds = \sigma_{22}^0 + A(t) .$$

This solution inserted into the equation for the component σ_{12} leads to

$$\sigma_{12}(t) = \sigma_{12}^0 + \sigma_{22}^0 t + \int_0^t A(s) ds = \sigma_{12}^0 + \sigma_{22}^0 t + B(t),$$

which is used to get the solution for the component

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_{11}(t) &= \sigma_{11}^0 + 2\sigma_{12}^0 t + \sigma_{22}^0 t^2 + 2 \int_0^t B(s) ds = \\ &= \sigma_{11}^0 + 2\sigma_{12}^0 t + \sigma_{22}^0 t^2 + C(t). \end{aligned}$$

At the exit of a degrader with thickness d the output σ -matrix has the following form :

$$\sigma^{out} = \begin{pmatrix} \sigma_{11}^0 + 2\sigma_{12}^0 d + \sigma_{22}^0 d^2 & \sigma_{12}^0 + \sigma_{22}^0 d \\ \sigma_{12}^0 + \sigma_{22}^0 d & \sigma_{22}^0 \end{pmatrix} + \begin{pmatrix} C & B \\ B & A \end{pmatrix}$$

where A means $A(t = d)$ and so on. The first matrix at the r. h. s. of this equation is the matrix produced by a drift space without matter. The second matrix (we will call it scattering matrix), which is independent of the input matrix, contains all the scattering action. Thus the entire action of the degrader can be replaced by a drift without matter and the addition of a degrader dependent matrix at one point (the degrader exit in equ.(11)). In order to simplify the last formula and the Optimization in the next chapter the input beam is characterized by the σ matrix σ^{in} describing the phase space of the beam, into which the input beam would convert in a drift space without matter. So we get

$$\sigma^{out} = \sigma^{in} + \begin{pmatrix} C & B \\ B & A \end{pmatrix} \quad (11)$$

The matrix σ^{in} of course occurs only in the absence of any degrader, but provides a lucid formalism for the calculation of the degrader angular scattering.

6 General Optimization for minimal Output Emittance

One is interested to know the input phase space ellipse corresponding to a given input emittance $\varepsilon_{\sigma, in}$, which leads to the minimal output emittance $\varepsilon_{\sigma, out}^{min}$ at the degrader exit. A minimal output emittance is equivalent to a minimal determinant of the output σ matrix

$$\det \sigma^{out} = (\varepsilon_{\sigma, in})^2 + (AC - B^2) + (A\sigma_{11}^{in} + C\sigma_{22}^{in} - 2B\sigma_{12}^{in}) .$$

The first (emittance of the input beam) and the second (depending only on the degrader) term in this formula are fixed, but the third term depends on the choosen shape of the input phase space. A minimum for this last term requires :

$$d(\det \sigma^{out}) = A d\sigma_{11}^{in} + C d\sigma_{22}^{in} - 2B d\sigma_{12}^{in} = 0$$

The constraint of the determined input emittance $\sigma_{11}^{in}\sigma_{22}^{in} - (\sigma_{12}^{in})^2 = \varepsilon_{\sigma, in}^2$ is rewritten as

$$\sigma_{22}^{in} d\sigma_{11}^{in} + \sigma_{11}^{in} d\sigma_{22}^{in} - 2\sigma_{12}^{in} d\sigma_{12}^{in} = 0 .$$

The last formula is used to eliminate $d\sigma_{12}^{in}$ in the formula for $d(\det \sigma_{out})$. If in the resulting equation $d\sigma_{11}^{in}$ and $d\sigma_{22}^{in}$ are set to zero separately, one obtains :

$$A \sigma_{12}^{in} = B \sigma_{22}^{in} \quad \text{and} \quad C \sigma_{12}^{in} = B \sigma_{11}^{in}$$

These relations determine the input phase space apart from a constant factor, which is defined by the input emittance $\varepsilon_{\sigma,in}$. So the optimized input beam gets :

$$\sigma_{in}^{opt} = \frac{\varepsilon_{\sigma,in}}{\sqrt{AC - B^2}} \begin{pmatrix} A & B \\ B & A \end{pmatrix} \quad (12)$$

This result implies, that the input beam has to be focused at the distance $t_{foc} = d - A/d$ after the entrance. The ratio of its spatial size to its angular size is $k = \sqrt{AC - B^2}/A$. This implies a spot size $\sqrt{\varepsilon_{\sigma,in} k}$. The optimized input σ - matrix is inserted into equ.(11) in order to get optimized output σ - matrix

$$\sigma_{out}^{opt} = \left(1 + \frac{\varepsilon_{\sigma,in}}{\sqrt{AC - B^2}} \right) \begin{pmatrix} C & B \\ B & A \end{pmatrix} \quad (13)$$

This corresponds to a beam diverging from a spot at the same point the input has to be focused on. The ratio of the spatial to the angular size is the same k as for the input beam.

From the optimized output σ -matrix the minimal output emittance $\varepsilon_{\sigma,out}$ is computed

$$\varepsilon_{\sigma,out}^{min} = \sqrt{\det(\sigma_{out}^{opt})} = \varepsilon_{\sigma,in} + \sqrt{AC - B^2} \quad (14)$$

This means, that for the optimized beam the emittance ε_{σ} is increased by a constant amount $\Delta\varepsilon_{\sigma}^{min} = \sqrt{AC - B^2}$ characteristic of the degrader.

7 Numerical Evaluation of the General Formulas

For the computation of the repeated integrals A, B and C the term $d \vartheta_{rms}^2 / dt$ w. r. t. the beam line length t is needed. If one wants to apply formula (3) this means that the function $p\beta(t)$ has to be calculated, which is a special form of a range curve and can be computed by the integration of an energy loss formula. In fig.2 $p\beta$ is plotted versus the stopping range r for a ^{12}C beam on different targets. To get this plot the range at different energies were read from an output file of Ziegler [7]. From this diagram one sees that for a wide range these curves may be quite accurately approximated by

$$p\beta = b r^{\alpha} \quad (15)$$

with constants b and α depending on the beam and the absorber material. In table 1 the constants for the curves in fig. 2 are listed. For the calculation of the constants the ranges for energies 500 and 75 MeV/nucl corresponding to $p\beta$ 144.4 and 825.3 MeV/(c nucl) were taken from Ziegler. b and α are fitted so, that these two points lie on the curve defined by equ. (15).

Figure 2: $p\beta$ (per nucleon) - range diagramm for a ^{12}C beam on different target materials

Table 1: Determination of the $p\beta$ - range curve coefficients in equ. (15) for a ^{12}C beam on different targets. The Radiation Length L_R and the density ρ are taken from ref. [6]. (For B_4C L_R was calculated the formula in [6] and data from [8])

material	$\frac{p\beta}{\text{MeV}/c}$	$\frac{r}{\text{cm}}$	$\frac{b}{\text{cm}^{-\alpha} \text{MeV}/c}$	α	$\frac{L_R}{\text{cm}}$	$\frac{\rho}{\text{g}/\text{cm}^3}$
Water	144.4	1.524	115.1	0.5392	36.1	1.00
	825.3	38.63				
Li	144.4	3.459	74.13	0.5374	155.	0.534
	825.3	88.66				
Graphit	144.4	0.759	167.6	0.5397	18.8	2.265
	825.3	19.18				
Be	144.4	1.012	143.5	0.5384	35.3	1.848
	825.3	25.87				
Pb	144.4	0.292	287.1	0.5584	0.56	11.35
	825.3	6.625				
B_4C	144.4	0.720	172.4	0.5395	19.9	2.52
	825.3	18.22				

Using equations (15) and (4) the integrals A , B and C can be calculated analytically :

$$A = -\frac{K}{b^2} \int_{R_i}^{R_f} \frac{1}{r^{2\alpha}} dr = \frac{K}{b^2(1-2\alpha)} [R_i^{1-2\alpha} - R_f^{1-2\alpha}] \quad (16)$$

$$B = \frac{K}{b^2} \int_{r=R_i}^{R_f} \left[\int_{s=R_i}^r \frac{1}{s^{2\alpha}} ds \right] dr = \frac{K}{b^2(1-2\alpha)(2-2\alpha)} [R_f^{2-2\alpha} - R_i^{2-2\alpha}] + \frac{K R_i^{1-2\alpha}(R_i - R_f)}{b^2(1-2\alpha)} \quad (17)$$

$$C = -2 \frac{K}{b^2} \int_{r=R_i}^{R_f} \left\{ \int_{s=R_i}^r \left[\int_{v=R_i}^s \frac{1}{v^{2\alpha}} dv \right] ds \right\} dr = \quad (18)$$

$$= \frac{2K [R_i^{3-2\alpha} - R_f^{3-2\alpha}]}{b^2(1-2\alpha)(2-2\alpha)(3-2\alpha)} - \frac{2K R_i^{2-2\alpha}(R_i - R_f)}{b^2(1-2\alpha)(2-2\alpha)} + \frac{K R_i^{1-2\alpha}(R_i - R_f)^2}{b^2(1-2\alpha)}$$

Here R_i (R_f) means the range of the beam before (after) the degrader in the absorber material.

In order to compare different degrader materials the numerical calculations are related to a given decrease of energy from an initial value T_i to a final value T_f . The ranges needed for equ. (16-18) are calculated using equ. (15). Some results are shown in table 2. Using equ. (15) and constants from table 1 the initial Energies 340 and 430 MeV/nuc correspond to water ranges 20.66 and 30.29 cm . The final Energies 200, 150, 100 MeV/nuc respectively correspond to water ranges of 8.49, 5.17, 2.54 cm , respectively.

Table 2: Different materials for the degradation of a ^{12}C beam. Degradation from initial energy T_i to final energy T_f requires a target thickness d . $\Delta\varepsilon_\sigma$ and k are the parameters for above derived Optimization the Optimization.

material	T_i MeV	T_f MeV	d cm	t_f cm	$\Delta\varepsilon_\sigma$ mm mrad	k cm
Water	430.	200.	21.8	13.3	6.6	6.58
		100.	27.8	19.5	16.4	7.52
	340.	200.	12.17	7.05	2.63	3.48
		150.	15.48	9.61	6.43	4.38
Li	430.	100.	18.11	12.24	9.32	4.99
		200.	50.1	30.6	8.1	14.2
	340.	100.	63.7	44.8	20.1	17.3
		200.	27.9	16.2	3.23	8.00
Graphit	430.	150.	35.5	22.0	6.43	10.0
		100.	41.5	28.1	11.4	11.5
	340.	200.	10.83	6.62	3.12	3.07
		100.	13.79	9.69	7.76	3.74
Be	430.	150.	7.69	4.77	2.49	2.17
		100.	9.00	6.08	4.42	2.48
	340.	200.	14.56	8.90	3.00	4.13
		100.	18.53	13.02	7.46	5.02
B_4C	430.	200.	8.12	4.70	1.20	2.32
		150.	10.33	6.41	2.39	2.92
	340.	100.	12.09	8.17	4.24	3.33
		200.	10.29	6.29	2.66	2.92
	430.	100.	13.10	9.20	6.62	3.55
		200.	5.74	3.33	1.06	1.64
	340.	150.	7.31	4.54	2.12	2.07
		100.	8.55	5.78	3.77	2.36

5.28

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